

THE ROLE OF THE MEDIA IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDIA EDUCATION IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS: INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Tailakova Shakhnoza Norbekovna

Head of the department in JMCUU, PhD, Associate Professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219214>

Abstract. *A new direction of education, in a word, education in the field of mass media and communication is media education. The term media education is used in a narrow context as a general cultural component of education. This is in line with the goals of general education. In pedagogy, the words media culture and news culture are also used as synonyms for the word media education. Today, news culture and media literacy are considered very topical issues. The article analyzes in detail the role of the media in the development of media education in secondary schools.*

Keywords: *general secondary education, media education, information culture, media literacy, mass media, pedagogical approaches.*

Introduction. A modern person is faced with a huge flow of information from childhood. Children are particularly susceptible to the influence of mass media, as they have not yet been able to filter information, distinguish fact from opinion and pure information from propaganda material. This means that the specialized mass media intended for the children's audience are of special importance to the society, their main task is the social responsibility that carries out the primary socialization of the individual.

Main part. UNESCO adopted the Media Education Declaration in 1982. According to it, "Media education is closely connected with all types of media (print, graphic, sound, screen, etc.) and various technologies. It gives people knowledge such as understanding how to use mass communication in social consciousness, mastering the skill of using media while communicating with other people.

Also, the following skills are formed:

- analysis, critical view and creation of media texts;
- identify the sources of media texts, their political, social, commercial or cultural interests in context;
- media texts distributed by the media and their importance interpretation;
- other suitable for creating their own media texts selection of media texts and finding an audience interested in it;
- to obtain the possibility of open access to the media". [1,39]

Media education is part of a person's right to receive and distribute information. UNESCO recommends introducing media education into the national curricula of the educational systems of all countries of the world. Currently, in countries such as European countries, the USA, Australia and Russia, media education is included in the education system as a compulsory subject. Organization of media education classes, forms and methods of the media education process in the audience of pupils and students of the monograph "Methodology and technology of media education at school and university" [2,67] by the teacher of Rostov State University of Economics

I.V. Chelysheva and technique section, the following example is given about the importance of periodicals in studying media education: "Another interesting way of working in class involving media sources can be review of scientific and technical articles in periodical press. Regularly, with the publication of one or another popular scientific magazine, schoolchildren introduce the audience to the most interesting publications orally or in writing (in the form of an abstract or creative work). Later, these works can be published in the school wall newspaper.

The word "media education" entered the territory of the CIS countries in the 80s of the last century. It is not appropriate to simply translate the English word "media education". It can be used in different meanings depending on its place in the text. Nevertheless, we need to define the basic concept of media education. A.A. Jurin divided them into three types:

1. Pedagogical science that studies the impact of mass media on children and adolescents and develops theoretical issues, prepares students for a meeting with the media world.
2. Joint practical activities of teachers and students preparing children and teenagers to understand the role of mass media in the world.
3. The part of education that provides knowledge about the role of mass media in understanding the culture and the world and forms the ability to effectively work with media information. [3,24]

Currently, media education is defined as an interdisciplinary field that combines a number of disciplines (pedagogy, sociology, psychology, linguistics), studies the laws of mass communication and the possibilities of using media resources by various social groups.

More than 200 children's newspapers and magazines are published in Russia. Therefore, in the typology of Russian children's publications, publications are divided into several groups according to the scale of distribution: publications distributed throughout Russia, publications distributed throughout the CIS countries and near foreign countries ("Пионер", "Мы", "Штучка", "Путеводная звезда", "Круто", "Tom and Jerry" and other magazines); Publications distributed throughout Russia and CIS countries ("Мурзилка", "Маруся", "Бумеранг", "Молоток", "Браво", "Yes!" etc. magazines); publications distributed only throughout Russia ("Для самых-самых маленьких", "Карапуз", etc. magazines); publications in Russian and national languages throughout the region, in most cases bilingually (90 such magazines are published in Russia today.

F.M.Dostoevsky once asked himself the following question: "Is it possible to accept the world without evil, but without children?" And he answers: It's better to leave everything as it is, but let it be with the children. Children hold the absurdity and evil in the world in balance. Man has a great, noble ability - to think about the future, regardless of whether it will happen in the future or not. Why? Because our children will live in the future. Children are the eternal theme of this world. They have always been at the center of humanity's main concerns, thoughts and hopes." [4,55]

Taking into account that it is impossible to completely separate children of today from Internet networks, especially Telegram, Instagram, Facebook, and especially YouTube, the magazine will inform about channels and pages with interesting and, most importantly, clear information for children in these networks, this channel and cooperation with pages is likely to create a positive creative environment. If today's children are used to getting information through the gadgets in their hands, it may be the most correct way to return them to printed publications with the help of these gadgets. Today, children's rights are regularly covered in the mass media of the world's leading countries. In November 1999, media workers, journalists, and experts on

children's rights gathered in Oslo, Norway, and sought answers to the question of how the media can contribute to the development of children's rights around the world, and they determined 5 directions in this regard. These directions are:

- the right of children to the mass media, as well as participation in the new mass media;
- children's right to education in media;
- children's right to media;
- the right of children to be protected from harm from media;
- the role of mass media in the protection and promotion of children's rights.

The point of children's right to be protected from harm from mass media is realized through the functions of children's media education. The Children's Information Provider acknowledges that children's publications may be held liable for violating this right. How children are portrayed in the media motivates the formation of such an attitude towards them in others. It is the media that can be the cause of positive or negative resolution of children's issues. In most cases, the media portrays children as passive, silent victims. Allowing children and adolescents to speak on their own behalf will lead to the formation of an opinion in the media about what they want, their achievements, and the issues they are thinking about. According to the information of the International Federation of Journalists, in the formation of children's images, the mass media in most cases use the same myth. [5,43] These are: the situation of families who have lost their individuality and humanity, living in developing countries, children living in poverty, victims of war and natural disasters. [6,36]

It can be effective to integrate media education with the science of "Education" in general education schools of Uzbekistan. In the continuous education system of Uzbekistan, it is appropriate to focus on increasing the effectiveness of using media education in pre-school educational institutions, schools, lyceums, vocational colleges, as well as higher educational institutions. What results can we achieve in this?

Based on the child's age and development, teaching to divide the media into types in a preschool educational institution:

verbal - viewing and observation: explaining the true nature of various cartoons, children's programs and shows;

non-verbal - listening information: interpreting the content of fairy tales, legends, stories and poems;

audiovisual - radio programs, interpreting the information on audio-recorded discs in a way understandable to children, in connection with real life [7,56]

it is necessary to convey the information belonging to these types of media to the child's consciousness in a simplified form, and most importantly, to teach the child to understand the difference between real life and the visual world.

In primary and secondary (5-6) grades:

be able to choose media forms and tools (for example, choosing and distinguishing photography, paintings, magazine illustrations); creating and defining a visual text or short plot plan (photo, video, comic, fairy tale, computer graphics, etc.)

prepare and present a presentation of their media project. [8,45]

In the upper grades of the school:

create different plots based on the photo (by changing the shape and elements of the photo);

making decisions regarding the use of available media (photo, video, press, etc.), discussing and justifying their decisions;

perform and present their own media project.

In academic lyceums and vocational colleges:

conducting experiments based on the use of special texts and "messaging" sending forms and technologies;

use of various techniques in the creation and planning of media texts, accurate and critical analysis of the result;

being able to create media products intended for a special audience, anticipating how that audience will receive them;

perform and present their own media project. Despite the concrete proposal for the issue 8 years ago, the problem is still relevant and unsolved.

In conclusion, the role of mass media in the development of media education in secondary schools today is a large number of newspapers and magazines on various topics for independent individuals. For children who are thirsty for knowledge and cannot distinguish white from black, the fact that there are only a few children's periodicals with an affordable price and content equal to gold is the most urgent problem. Encouraging children to think should not be limited to fiction.

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